

Reading strategies that help you in IELTS exam

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Annotation: Reading tasks are important to understand students' overall reading abilities. These tasks will be used for student placement, policy decisions, curriculum changes, and program, student, teacher or institutional evaluations. The IELTS Reading test consists of 40 questions, designed to test a wide range of reading skills. These include reading for gist, reading for main ideas, reading for detail, skimming, understanding logical argument and recognising writers' opinions, attitudes and purpose. We know that reading is one of the most challenging tasks of IELTS and we can say that there are many strategies which are considered so helpful.

Keywords: Scanning, skimming, reading skills, strong vocabulary

As we mentioned already, Reading includes many strategies and now we will see some of them. One of the most important strategy is scanning. Scanning is reading rapidly in order to find specific facts. Skimming tells you what general information is within a sections. One important feature of scanning can be that it helps you locate a particular fact. Skimming is like snorkeling, and scanning is more like pearl diving. The purpose of scanning documents is to have an easy way to save, store, and protect critical data; it helps save time and money. Document scanning and archiving is a very important step in your record management system. It gives you an invaluable layer of protection for your documents, files, and records. Once the paperwork is scanned, it can be archived, stored offsite, or securely destroyed. With this system that addresses the entire lifecycle of a document, you'll be taking the necessary steps to protect company and personal data. Because skimming is done at a fast speed with less-than-normal comprehension, you shouldn't skim all the time. There are many times, however, when skimming is very useful. [1]

The next important strategy could be skimming. Skimming is one of the tools you can use to read more in less time. Skimming refers to looking only for the general or main ideas, and works best with non-fiction (or factual) material. With skimming, your overall understanding is reduced because you don't read everything. You read only what is important to your purpose. Skimming takes place while reading and allows you to look for details in addition to the main ideas. Skimming will help you locate the information quickly while making sure you use your time wisely. It will also increase the amount of usable material you obtain for your research.

Suppose you have an exam in a few days. You need to review the material you learned, but you don't want to reread everything. By skimming, you can quickly locate the information you haven't mastered yet and study only that material.

As the word "skim" means "to read quickly" and one interesting fact about skimming is that the criminals use various devices, known as skimmers, to steal data without the victim even realising it. This is usually carried out when making transactions at an ATM or paying at a point-of-sale (POS) terminal that has been tampered with beforehand. [2]

One of the next important strategy can be Predicting. Predicting is an important reading strategy. It allows students to use information from the text, such as titles, headings, pictures and

diagrams to anticipate what will happen in the story [3]. When making predictions, students envision what will come next in the text, based on their prior knowledge. A reader involved in making predictions is focused on the text at hand, constantly thinking ahead and also refining, revising, and verifying his or her predictions. This strategy also helps students make connections between their prior knowledge and the text. Prediction can keep children engaged in the story and helps readers to make connections between their prior knowledge and the text. It ensures that the child is able to understand what they are reading as they try and make logical and reasonable assumptions about what could happen next.

How to Make Predictions?

The best way to encourage readers to make logical predictions is by prompting them to look at what has already happened in the text. This will help them to extract what the characters may have hinted is coming up or what may have been implied by the author's use of language.

The last strategy that should be mentioned is intensive reading. As the name suggests, intensive reading refers to reading short texts thoroughly and with clear goals, such as to answer reading comprehension questions or to identify how sentences are linked. Unlike extensive reading, the goal of intensive reading is not to read many texts for fluency, but rather to read a shorter piece of text to gain a deeper understanding of that text.

Although reading comprehension can be one goal of intensive reading, its goals may include learning subject matter, vocabulary learning and studying the authors' intentions. In other words, the goal of intensive reading is not limited to reading comprehension.[4]

References:

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